

Ethnobotanical Studies of Dholpur-Karauli Tiger Reserve (Rajasthan) India

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Abstract

Dholpur-Karauli is the fifth tiger reserve area after Ranthambore, Sariska, Mukundra Hills and Ramgarh Vishdhari tiger reserve of Rajasthan state. A survey of medicinal plants has been carried out from Dholpur-Karauli tiger reserve in this paper. Total of 101 medicinal plants have been identified as useful in medicinal field from this reserve area. All these medicinal plants have been explained with their local name, family and uses in medicinal fields. Several medicinal plant species this tiger reserve area are on the verge of extinction due to different developmental activities, overgrazing, encroachments and unsustainable uses. People are unaware from the importance of medicinal uses of these plants in this region due to lack of awareness and research work. In this Tiger Reserve area dominantly found mixed deciduous plant species such as *Acacia catechu*, *Anogeissus pendula*, *Butea monosperma*, *Lannaea coromendelica*, etc.

Keywords Tiger Reserve, Ethnobotanical, Inhabitants, Extinction, Diversity, Medicinal uses.

Introduction

The Dholpur-Karauli Tiger Reserve area is joint to Ranthambore in Rajasthan and attached with some area of Madhya Pradesh. It has a total of 1,075 sq km area with 580 sq km core area and 495 sq km buffer area. A total of eight tigers are present in this tiger reserve. Above than 5000 peoples located who are living in this reserve area. The tiger reserve area attached with the Chambal River. The Chambal River which makes divide line between Rajasthan and Madhya Pradesh also become part of this reserve area. Exclude some part from tiger reserve area that falls in the periphery from firing range. Chambal corridors have successfully protected for tiger reserve area by the forest department.

Aim of study

This study was aimed to recognize the medicinal properties of studied area and know about the importance of medicinal plants for better human health.

Review of Literature

This is my original research work and no prior studies have been done the same topic. So latest review references are not available.

Main Text

Study Area

To know the position of tiger reserve area a field survey was carried out and show in Dholpur and Karauli districts located between $26^{\circ}23'$ to $26^{\circ}70'$ latitude and $76^{\circ}05'$ to $77^{\circ}89'$ longitude. Sapotara, Mandrail and Karauli tehsil of Karauli district, Bari and Baseri tehsil of Dholpur district were surveyed. During the survey of study a total of thirty eight villages were notified. To know local ethnobotanical knowledge and documenting the medicinal plants carried out regular visit for at many times.